

POTASSIUM METAPERIODATE AS A VOLUMETRIC REAGENT.
PART IV. IODINE CYANIDE METHOD

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Potassium metaperiodate has been used as an oxidising reagent in the volumetric estimation of potassium iodide, hydrazine sulphate, stannous chloride, potassium ferricyanide, hydrogen peroxide, arsenious oxide, tartar emetic, hydroquinone, potassium sulphocyanide, ferrous ammonium sulphate, sodium thiosulphate, sodium sulphite, sodium bisulphite, sulphurous acid, lead iodide, mercuric iodide and silver iodide by the iodine cyanide method.

Potassium metaperiodate in acid solution is a strong oxidising agent. It is reduced to iodine.

The iodine is oxidised by the periodate

The end of the titration is reached through this reaction, whose completion is shown, in the presence of a suitable indicator (starch), by the disappearance of the free iodine. In the presence of hydrogen cyanide, the cation I^+ changes at once into stable iodine cyanide.

This method therefore is based on titration with the periodate in the presence of hydrogen cyanide, the periodate being quantitatively converted into iodine cyanide.

In presence of potassium cyanide and hydrochloric acid, potassium metaperiodate reacts in accordance with the equations :

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Potassium metaperiodate was prepared by the method of Bahl and Singh (this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 167).

A known weight of each substance in solution was taken in a stoppered conical flask. About 8 c. c. of 0.5*N*-KCN, at least 50 c. c. of 2.5*N*-HCl, about 1 g. of sodium chloride and some starch solution were added and the titration with *M*/60-KIO₄ was carried out to the discharge of the iodine-starch blue colour, which appeared at the beginning of the titration. In these titrations normality of the solution with respect to hydrochloric acid was maintained at about 1*N*.

All the substances, except potassium iodide, hydrazine sulphate, stannous chloride, lead iodide, mercuric iodide and silver iodide were pre-oxidised before titration. Potassium ferrocyanide and hydrogen peroxide were pre-oxidised with hypo-iodous acid (5 c. c. of 0.5*N*-ICl and 20 c. c. of 10% NaOH) in an alkaline medium and after pre-oxidation the solutions were acidified with hydrochloric acid. The rest of the substances were pre-oxidised with 5 c. c. of 0.5*N*-ICl in presence of hydrochloric acid.

In the case of sodium thiosulphate, sodium sulphite, sodium bisulphite and sulphurous acid, the titration mixture was cooled in ice-cold water and titrated rapidly against standard potassium metaperiodate until a distinct iodine-starch blue colour was imparted to the solution. The titration was then continued slowly with thorough shaking till the discharge of the blue colour. In case of titration of large quantities of these substances, their solutions were added to 10 to 15 c. c. of iodine monochloride contained in a titration flask. Iodine monochloride reacted with them quantitatively liberating iodine and thus prevented the loss of sulphur dioxide during the titration. The liberated iodine was titrated as usual against standard potassium metaperiodate solution in presence potassium cyanide.

Lead iodide (up to 0.4 g.) was dissolved in a small amount of sodium hydroxide solution, acidified with 20 c. c. of 1:1 hydrochloric acid and titrated against standard potassium metaperiodate solution in presence of 10 to 15 c. c. of potassium cyanide and a few c. c. of starch solution.

Mercuric iodide (up to 0.4 g.) was dissolved in potassium cyanide solution, acidified with 12 c. c. of 1:1 hydrochloric acid and titrated against standard potassium metaperiodate in presence of starch solution.

Silver iodide (up to 0.4 g.) was dissolved in 10 c. c. of potassium cyanide solution and reduced at the boiling point to metallic silver with iron free zinc in presence of a little sodium hydroxide. When the reduction was complete, the suspension was filtered and the precipitate washed with water and dilute hydrochloric acid. The filtrate was acidified with 12 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and titrated against standard potassium metaperiodate solution after the addition of starch as an indicator.

Several titrations were performed in each case. From the volume of potassium metaperiodate used, corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each substance was calculated. The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I

Potassium iodide			Hydrazine sulphate.		
M/60-KIO ₄ .	taken	found.	M/60-KIO ₄	taken.	found.
13.0 c.c.	0.10793 g.	0.10788 g.	15.0 c.c.	0.04876 g.	0.04873 g.
22.0	0.18266	0.18257	25.0	0.08127	0.08123
50.0	0.41515	0.41499	40.1	0.13000	0.13028
Stannous chloride.			Potassium ferrocyanide		
SnCl ₂ · 2H ₂ O			K ₄ Fe (CN) ₆ · 3H ₂ O		
13.50 c.c.	0.1520 g.	0.1525 g.	10.00 c.c.	0.4210 g.	0.4220 g.
24.70	0.2800	0.2791	17.00	0.7174	0.7174
33.40	0.3775	0.3775	30.85	1.3082	1.3079
Hydrogen peroxide.			Arsenious oxide.		
16.30 c.c.	0.002774 g.	0.00277	10.00 c.c.	0.0495 g.	0.0494 g.
24.40	0.00414	0.00414	27.10	0.1336	0.1341
36.80	0.00629	0.00625	43.10	0.2128	0.2133
Tartar emetic.			Hydroquinone.		
10.10 c.c.	0.1669 g.	0.1686	10.00 c.c.	0.0550 g.	0.0550 g.
25.20	0.4175	0.4208	20.00	0.1100	0.1100
37.30	0.6179	0.6229	38.00	0.2035	0.2090

TABLE II

Potassium sulphocyanide			Ferrous ammonium sulphate.		
M/60-KIO ₄	taken.	found.	M/60-KIO ₄ .	taken.	found.
10.15 c.c.	0.01617 g.	0.01640 g.	10.65 c.c.	0.04175 g.	0.04174 g.
25.00	0.04042	0.04040	21.30	0.08343	0.08349
33.10	0.05336	0.05348	30.50	0.11958	0.11956
Sodium thiosulphate			Sodium sulphite.		
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ · 5H ₂ O			Na ₂ SO ₃		
10.00	0.0310 g.	0.0310 g.	15.00 c.c.	0.09451 g.	0.09451 g.
23.00	0.0713	0.0713	20.00	0.12602	0.12602
37.00	0.1147	0.1147	30.00	0.18903	0.18903
Sodium bisulphite.			Sulphurous acid.		
20.00	0.1040 g.	0.1040 g.	10.00	0.04102 g.	0.04102 g.
26.00	0.1352	0.1352	21.10	0.08655	0.08655
40.10	0.2080	0.2085	33.00	0.13536	0.13536
Lead iodide.			Mercuric iodide		
10.00	0.1153 g.	0.1153 g.	10.00	0.1137 g.	0.1137 g.
20.10	0.2306	0.2318	23.00	0.2620	0.2615
30.10	0.3460	0.3470	30.00	0.3411	0.3411

TABLE III

AgI taken.	M/60-KIO ₄ used.	AgI found.
0.2000 g.	17.00 c.c.	0.1997 g.
0.2820	24.00	0.2820
0.3900	33.30	0.3912

From the above results it is concluded that potassium iodide, hydrazine sulphate, stannous chloride, potassium ferrocyanide, hydrogen peroxide, arsenious oxide, tartar emetic, hydroquinone, potassium sulphocyanide, ferrous ammonium sulphate, sodium thiosulphate, sodium sulphite, sodium bisulphite, sulphurous acid, lead iodide, mercuric iodide and silver iodide can be determined quantitatively by the iodine cyanide method, using potassium metaperiodate as a volumetric reagent.

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